

BUSINESS LAW

LIMITED COMPANIES

EDITELY EDITION

Romina Abril (47590561L)

Iván Vareniza(Z1676601K)

Index:

Introduction.....	3
The advantages and disadvantages of the S.L.....	3
Features of the S.L.....	4
Comparison with other types of companies.....	5
Context of the Capital Companies Act.....	14
The steps to follow to establish a company.....	14
The governing and management bodies.....	17
Conclusion.....	17
Citations.....	19

Introduction.

This legal report examines the feasibility and process for establishing a Limited Liability Company (LLC) by Lara Simó Roca and her brother, Roger Simó Roca, both residents of Barcelona. With the intention of starting a shampoo sales business, this thesis will analyze the advantages and disadvantages of this legal form, its main characteristics, and the steps required for its incorporation. The Capital Companies Act and other applicable regulations will be used as a reference. The distribution of share capital is also detailed, with a contribution of €15,000 by Ms. Simó and €5,000 by Mr. Simó.

The advantages and disadvantages of the S.L.

A Limited Liability Company (LLC), classified as a capital company and a common option for establishing SMEs, is characterized by its capital divided into shares. The partners' liability is limited to the contributions made, and they are not personally liable for company debts with their assets, except in cases of tax or Social Security. Among its main advantages is this limitation of liability, which protects the partners' personal assets. Additionally, it offers flexibility in terms of capital structure, as it does not impose minimum or maximum percentages per partner beyond their share capital contribution, nor does it limit the minimum number of working partners, allowing for the inclusion of individuals or legal entities. The organization of the governing body is also adaptable, and it is even possible to appoint a permanent director.

However, limited liability companies have certain drawbacks. A minimum initial share capital of €3,000 is required, which can be contributed in either cash or assets. This minimum capital, while a relatively low barrier to entry, can be perceived as a limited guarantee for creditors, whose collection capacity is restricted to the share capital. Furthermore, limited liability companies are better suited to a small number of partners involved, given that entry and exit tend to be more restrictive. This limitation is particularly evident when transferring shares to third parties, since, before proceeding with the sale, the intention must be communicated to the other partners, who have a preemptive right of acquisition.

Features of the S.L.

A Limited Liability Company (S.L.) is a commercial capital company whose legal regime is primarily governed by the Capital Companies Act. Its name can be abbreviated

interchangeably as SL or SRL. A distinctive feature is the limited liability of its partners, who are only liable for contributions made to the share capital, thus protecting their personal assets. SLs allow the sole proprietorship, whether from its inception or subsequently, and can be part of groups of companies. Share capital is divided into contributions.

The internal functioning of a limited company is governed by two main bodies: the General Meeting of Shareholders and the Board of Directors. The General Meeting is the supreme body representing all shareholders and where the most important decisions are made through different types of majorities. These may be ordinary legal majorities (more votes in favor than against, representing at least one-third of the share capital), reinforced legal majorities (requiring more than 50% or even two-thirds of the share capital for key decisions such as bylaw amendments, capital increases/reductions, transformation, mergers, or exclusion of shareholders), or reinforced statutory majorities (established in the bylaws with percentages higher than the legal limit but not reaching unanimity). The General Meeting must be convened at least once a year within the first six months for the approval of accounts, and Extraordinary and Universal Majorities are also available. The meeting must be called by the directors or a minimum of 5% of the share capital. The meeting must be called at least fifteen days in advance in the municipality where the company is located. The meeting must be announced with the agenda and date, and must be published in the Official Gazette of the Commercial Registry or a newspaper.

For its part, the administrative body is responsible for the daily management and representation of the company. It can take various forms, such as a sole director, several directors acting jointly, or a board of directors, the organization of which may be provided for in the bylaws or decided by the General Meeting. Those exercising administration must meet certain capacity requirements and not be subject to legal prohibitions (such as unemancipated minors, incapacitated persons, officials with incompatibility, judges, or those convicted of certain crimes). Directors are accountable to the General Meeting, which has the power to remove them, and are subject to liability to the company, shareholders, and creditors for breaches such as failing to call the General Meeting or breaching their duty of loyalty. Finally, registration in the Commercial Registry is an essential requirement for a limited company.

Comparison with other types of companies.

Limited Company VS S.L.:

When setting up a company, one of the key aspects is choosing the legal form. Among the most notable are the Limited Liability Company (S.L.) and the Public Limited Company (S.A.), both of which are known as capital companies. Although they share certain fundamental elements, they present notable differences in terms of their structure, operation, legal requirements, and suitability depending on the type of business activity.

Both limited liability companies and limited partnerships offer limited liability to their partners or shareholders, meaning they are not liable for the company's debts with their personal assets, except in exceptional cases such as tax or Social Security obligations. This characteristic, common to both forms, is an advantage over sole proprietorships or self-employed businesses, where liability is unlimited.

However, the way in which the share capital is structured clearly distinguishes the two entities. In a limited company, the capital is divided into shares, which cannot be freely transferred, as the partners have a preemptive right of acquisition. This promotes internal stability and trust among the partners involved, although it can hinder the entry of new investors. In contrast, in a limited company, the capital is divided into shares, which can be freely transferred once the company is registered with the Commercial Registry, allowing greater flexibility in attracting investors and facilitating the transfer of ownership.

An important difference lies in the minimum share capital. While a limited company requires a minimum of €3,000, a limited company raises this minimum to €60,000, which represents a much higher barrier to entry and limits this option to larger companies or those with a significant growth prospect. This high initial capital requirement for limited companies is justified, in part, by their focus on raising public funds through the issuance of shares or bonds.

The internal structure and corporate bodies also vary. In both companies, the General Meeting (of partners in the Limited Company, of shareholders in the Limited Company) is the supreme deliberative and decision-making body. It meets regularly within the first six months of the year to approve accounts, review management, and decide on the distribution of profits. However, in the Limited Company, the convening process is more formal, requiring publication in the Official Gazette of the Commercial Registry and in a widely circulated newspaper, while in the Limited Company, less formal means are sufficient if established in the bylaws.

The governing body can take different forms in both cases: a sole director, several joint directors, or a board of directors. However, SAs are more rigid and formal, as their complexity and size often require a board with greater oversight and specialization. Furthermore, in SAs, directors must comply with a series of stricter obligations, such as preparing and signing the annual accounts, drafting the management report, and filing the accounting documentation with the Commercial Registry.

Regarding the transfer of ownership, in limited companies this transaction is restricted and usually requires the consent of the other partners, which can represent an obstacle to outside investment. In contrast, joint-stock companies allow the free circulation of shares, making them the ideal option for large companies seeking to attract outside capital, especially through financial markets.

One point of agreement between the two is that they can be incorporated as single-member companies, although in SA this entails a series of additional obligations, such as the explicit identification of the sole shareholder in the Commercial Registry, greater publicity, and greater liability in certain cases.

Regarding the participation and rights of partners or shareholders, there are also nuances. In a limited company, shareholders have rights such as the right to participate in profits, the right to the distribution of assets in the event of liquidation, preferential rights in the subscription of new shares, voting rights, and the right to information. These rights are more developed and guaranteed by law than in a limited company, where, while they also exist, they have a simpler approach and are more adapted to an environment with fewer partners.

In short, a Limited Company is best suited to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with a small number of partners, limited initial capital, and active participation by partners in management. It offers organizational flexibility and legal certainty without significant financial demands. A Public Limited Company, on the other hand, is designed for larger, more ambitious projects with more ambitious financing needs and a more professional structure open to investors.

The choice between a limited company and a limited liability company should therefore be based on the size of the company, the initial investment level, the desired organizational structure, and the future growth strategy. Both offer significant advantages, but also pose different challenges that must be carefully considered before making a final decision.

Non-profit associations vs. S.L.:

Compared to Limited Liability Companies (LLCs), both Non-profit Associations and Partnerships present substantial differences, as they respond to very different legal, economic, and social purposes.

On the one hand, a non-profit association does not aim to generate profits for its members, unlike a limited company, which is established for commercial and profit-making purposes. In a limited company, members seek financial returns in proportion to their shareholding, while in an association, the financial surplus must be fully reinvested in the fulfillment of its corporate purposes. Furthermore, in a limited company, members hold shares, which represent their share of the capital, while in an association, members do not hold ownership rights over the entity's assets.

Another key difference is asset liability: in a partnership, partners are not personally liable for the entity's debts, which is also the case with a limited liability company, as in both cases liability is limited to the assets of the legal entity. However, the internal workings vary, as a limited liability company has a corporate structure with a General Meeting of partners and a governing body that can take various forms (sole director, several joint directors, joint directors, or a council). In contrast, in a partnership, the General Meeting is the supreme body, a Board of Directors is the governing body, and a President is the legal representative.

Furthermore, limited companies require a minimum share capital of €3,000, while partnerships do not have a legal minimum, making them easier to establish for smaller-scale projects or those with limited initial resources. Furthermore, while the transfer of shares in limited companies is subject to restrictions and the preemptive right of shareholders, this does not apply to partnerships, as the shareholders do not have any economic shares to transfer.

On the other hand, when comparing a general partnership with a limited liability company, we find a very marked contrast in terms of the partners' liability. In a limited liability company, as its name suggests, the partners' liability is limited to the capital contributed, while in a general partnership, the partners are jointly and severally liable with all their present and future assets. This implies a much greater risk for the general partner, who must assume the debts if the company cannot pay them.

Furthermore, in limited companies, partners can be individuals or legal entities, and their direct involvement in management is not required. In contrast, a partnership is personal in nature,

with partners typically actively and equally involved in management. This characteristic reinforces the idea of trust among partners, but also implies that partner status is non-transferable, which restricts the entry of new members or growth through external investment, which is more feasible in limited companies.

Regarding incorporation, limited companies require a public deed and registration in the Commercial Registry, with a structure governed by the Capital Companies Act. Partnerships also require registration, but lack a minimum capital requirement, making them easier to establish, albeit at the cost of assuming greater personal risks. Limited companies, on the other hand, although they require a minimum capital requirement, offer greater asset protection and a more flexible organizational structure.

In short, both partnerships and general partnerships clearly differ from limited companies based on their purpose, risk level, structure, and legal requirements. Limited companies represent an intermediate form that combines flexibility, asset protection, and economic viability, as opposed to the altruistic and non-profit nature of partnerships and the high personal commitment and asset risk of general partnerships.

Collective Society VS S.L.:

A general partnership, unlike a limited company (S.L.), is characterized by its personal nature, in which the partners not only contribute capital or labor, but also directly commit to the management and development of the company. While in a limited company, the partners' liability is limited to the capital contributed, in a general partnership, liability is subsidiary, unlimited, and joint, which means that the partners must be liable with all their personal assets if the company is unable to meet its debts.

Furthermore, in an SL, shares are transferable—albeit with certain restrictions and preemptive rights for the other partners—but in a general partnership, the status of shareholder is non-transferable, as it is based on personal trust between members. This limits the entry of new partners and hinders business expansion through outside investment, which is more feasible in a SL.

In terms of structure, limited liability companies allow for various forms of management (sole director, several joint directors, joint directors, or a board of directors), and it's common for partners not to be directly involved in management. In contrast, in a general partnership, all

partners participate equally, with shared and direct management. This equal participation can facilitate decision-making, but it can also slow down the process in the event of disagreement.

Regarding initial capital, limited companies require a legal minimum of €3,000, which can be contributed in cash or assets, while partnerships do not require a minimum capital, which lowers the barriers to entry for incorporation. This ease of incorporation, however, is offset by a higher level of equity risk for partners.

Regarding the number of partners, limited companies do not require a high minimum number and can even be single-member, allowing for flexibility in their formation. A general partnership requires at least two partners, with no legal maximum, which can be beneficial for growth if the bond of trust between members is maintained.

Finally, from a legal and administrative perspective, limited companies are governed by the Capital Companies Act and have a more formal and structured legal regime, which provides greater legal certainty vis-à-vis third parties. Although general partnerships are also commercial companies and must be registered with the Commercial Registry, they have a simpler system in terms of procedures and accounting, which facilitates initial management.

In short, an LLC provides a more flexible, risk-limiting structure suitable for growth-oriented companies, while a partnership is a more direct, simple, and committed model, but with a very high level of risk due to the full financial liability of its partners. The choice between the two will depend on the level of trust between partners, the nature of the project, and risk tolerance.

Sociedad Comunitaria VS S.L.:

A limited partnership, unlike a limited company (S.L.), is based on a combination of personal and capitalist elements by integrating two distinct types of partners: general partners, who are personally and unlimitedly liable for the company's debts, and limited partners, whose liability is limited to the capital contributed and who have no involvement in the company's management. This duality allows for attracting external capital without losing operational control, something more difficult in a limited company, where all partners have political and economic rights proportional to their stakes.

While a limited partnership is a purely capitalist company where all partners have the same limited liability regime, a limited partnership introduces a key distinction based on the

partner's level of involvement in management. This structure is especially useful when it is desired to separate capital and management, allowing the general partners to run the company while the limited partners invest without intervening, something that is not clearly separated in a limited partnership.

In terms of liability, limited partnerships offer full protection for partners' personal assets, as they are only liable up to the limit of their contributions. In contrast, general partners in limited partnerships assume subsidiary, unlimited, and joint liability, which significantly increases the level of asset risk, just as in a general partnership. This can deter many entrepreneurs, while limited partners enjoy similar protection to partners in limited partnerships, albeit with fewer management rights.

From an administrative perspective, both companies can have a simple structure, especially the limited partnership, which does not require complex bodies. Limited partnerships, on the other hand, have a more regulated framework, with the possibility of configuring different forms of management (sole director, several joint directors, board, etc.) as provided in the bylaws. However, limited partnerships with shares are closer to the complexity of a public limited company, requiring share capital and being subject to a more rigid regime, thus losing some of the initial simplicity.

Regarding minimum capital, limited partnerships require a minimum contribution of €3,000, while limited partnerships do not require a minimum legal capital, which can facilitate their formation. However, limited partnerships with shares require the capital to be divided into shares and meet similar requirements as those of a public limited company, which increases costs and legal requirements.

Regarding profit sharing and decision-making, in a limited partnership, all partners participate according to their percentage of capital, while in a limited partnership, the limited partners do not participate in management or ordinary decisions, unless otherwise provided in the bylaws. This can be seen as an advantage in terms of role clarity, but it also limits the control of the investing partner.

In short, a Limited Partnership offers a balanced, secure, and flexible structure, ideal for entrepreneurs who wish to limit personal risks and maintain control proportional to the capital contributed. In contrast, a Limited Partnership represents a hybrid option that combines personal control with capital raising, making it useful for projects where some partners provide

management and others only provide financing. However, its effectiveness will depend on the balance between the interests of both types of partners and the risk tolerance of the groups.

Property Company VS S.L.:

The difference between a joint property company (CB) and a limited company (SL) is primarily in their legal nature, internal organization, and liability regime. A CB lacks its own legal personality, so the assets, rights, and obligations are directly linked to the joint owners, while a limited company is a legal entity distinct from its partners, providing a clear legal and asset separation.

In a joint property agreement, the joint owners act on their own behalf before third parties, which means that the joint property cannot enter into contracts or be a party to legal proceedings as a separate entity, while a limited liability company can operate with full legal autonomy. Furthermore, a joint property agreement arises from a contract between the joint owners, which can even be verbal, while a limited liability company requires a public deed and registration in the Commercial Registry, granting it greater formality and legal security.

A fundamental difference is the partners' liability. In a CB, it is unlimited, personal, and joint, meaning that the co-owners are liable with all their present and future assets for debts incurred on behalf of the community. In contrast, in a SL, the partners are only liable up to the limit of their contributions, without compromising their personal assets, which represents a significant advantage in terms of risk protection.

Regarding minimum capital, a CB does not require any minimum initial contribution, making it a flexible and economical option for starting a joint venture. However, this informality also entails greater risks and a weaker organizational structure. In contrast, a SL requires a minimum contribution of €3,000, which provides an initial financial base that strengthens the business's viability.

From a management and decision-making perspective, in a CB, benefits and liabilities are distributed proportionally to the shares held by each co-owner, and decisions are often made by consensus, which can lead to conflict if there are no clear rules. A SL, on the other hand, allows for a professionalized governance structure, with bodies such as the board of shareholders and directors, which facilitates decision-making and business growth.

Another notable difference lies in the level of confidentiality and public visibility. A CB operates through private and secret agreements between the owners, and is not required to make its accounts or operations public. A SL, on the other hand, must file annual accounts and comply with commercial obligations, which guarantees greater transparency, especially useful in relationships with banks, suppliers, and investors.

In short, a joint property partnership is a suitable option for small business ventures between trusted individuals, with a simple structure and no significant legal requirements, but also with a high level of risk and asset exposure. A limited company, although more formal and with stricter requirements, offers greater security, asset separation, and growth opportunities, making it the preferred option for more ambitious or long-term business projects.

Cooperative Society VS S.L.:

The Cooperative Society (S.C.) and the Limited Company (S.L.) differ primarily in their purpose, internal structure, and organizational principles. While the Limited Company (S.L.) is oriented toward generating economic benefits for its members in proportion to their shareholding, the Cooperative Society (S.C.) is founded with a mutualistic objective: to provide services or develop business activities for the direct benefit of its members, prioritizing cooperation over profit.

In cooperatives, operations are governed by democratic management principles, with each member typically having one vote, regardless of their capital contribution. This clearly distinguishes it from limited companies, where voting rights are allocated based on share capital. This gives cooperatives a more egalitarian structure, but can also make decision-making difficult when there are many members.

Regarding incorporation, the cooperative acquires legal personality upon registration in the Registry of Cooperative Societies, at which point the minimum share capital established in its bylaws must be fully paid up. In contrast, a limited company is established by public deed and registration in the Commercial Registry, with a legal minimum capital of €3,000, which must also be fully subscribed and paid up.

Regarding the liability of partners, in both limited partnerships and limited companies, this is limited to the capital contributed, which is an advantage over legal forms with unlimited

liability, such as joint property or general partnerships. This limitation provides both structures with greater security for partners against potential business debts.

Regarding share capital, the cooperative allows contributions not only in cash, but also in assets or rights with economic value, if so stated in the bylaws, which provides greater flexibility in financing. In limited companies, although non-cash contributions may also be accepted, these are subject to stricter legal requirements and require an objective valuation.

One significant difference lies in the distribution of profits: in cooperatives, profits are typically distributed based on participation in the cooperative's activities (e.g., purchases, sales, or labor), not based on capital participation, as is the case in limited companies. Furthermore, in limited companies, it is common to allocate part of the profits to mandatory reserve funds and for education and development, reflecting their social and community spirit.

Finally, cooperatives can benefit from tax incentives and specific subsidies, especially in sectors such as agriculture, education, or the social economy. This can provide an economic advantage over limited companies, although it also entails a greater degree of administrative oversight and more specific legal requirements depending on the autonomous community.

In short, a cooperative society is a suitable option when seeking democratic management, a mutual purpose, and equitable distribution of profits from participation in the activity. A limited company, on the other hand, is more oriented toward conventional for-profit business projects with control proportional to the capital invested, offering greater flexibility in decision-making and a more professional corporate structure.

Context of the Capital Companies Act.

After highlighting the advantages and disadvantages of the company we chose as the most suitable for the siblings, and how it compares to the others, it is essential to explain the legal framework that exclusively regulates such companies in Spain. The fundamental legislation in this area is the Capital Companies Law (LSC), which specifically governs the different types of companies considered capital companies: the public limited company, the limited liability company, and the partnership limited by shares. These legal entities share essential characteristics, highlighting first and foremost their separate legal personality, independent of that of their founding partners. Additionally, they possess share capital, constituted by the partners' contributions at the time of founding, which not only acts as primary security against

third-party creditors but also defines the scope of each partner's individual liability for the company's debts. Indeed, the nature of a capital company as an entity with its own assets means that liability for corporate obligations is limited to said assets and to the contributions made (whether in the form of shares or equity interests), thereby safeguarding the partners' private assets. The specific legal form adopted by a capital company can also influence the management and operational capacity of the partners within it, which is often restricted by their financial stake in the entity.

The steps to follow to establish a company.

Considering that the type of company to be run is an S.L. will be required completion of various procedures within the established deadlines, in accordance with the Capital Companies Act and other applicable regulations. This rigorous procedure not only seeks to guarantee legal certainty but also lays the foundation for the commercial activity in the shampoo sector that the future partners intend to develop.

First, the 'negative name certificate'. This procedure consists of obtaining a certificate that ensures that the name chosen for the limited company does not match that of any other registered company. This procedure is carried out at the Central Commercial Registry and can be done in person, by mail, or through the official website (www.rmc.es). To do so, you must submit the name of one of the promoters, propose up to three names, and specify that you are establishing a Limited Company. Once issued, the certificate is valid for six months from the date of issue and must be requested using the "Certification Request" form.

The next step is 'opening a bank account and depositing share capital'. Once the name has been approved, a bank account is opened in the name of the company, into which the required minimum share capital will be deposited—in this case, the total of €20,000, corresponding to the contributions of Ms. Lara Simó Roca (€15,000) and Mr. Roger Simó Roca (€5,000). This deposit is made in a financial institution and requires the provision of the holders' identification data (NIF or CIF), information on the fund disposition system, the signing of the contract, and the submission of the signature registration form, formalizing through the bank account contract.

Next comes the drafting of the bylaws, a document that will establish the internal operating rules of the limited company. These bylaws will also regulate the distribution of the share capital (which, in principle, taking into account the amount contributed by each

shareholder, would most logically be 75% for Ms. Lara Simo Roca and the other 25% for Mr. Roger Simo Roca. This distribution must be clearly stipulated in the public deed and the bylaws, ensuring that each partner has a share proportional to their contribution, which will impact economic and voting rights) and the shareholdings, a crucial aspect given the differences in the partners' contributions. The drafting must be done before a notary and requires the presentation of the founding partners' identification documents. It must be completed within a maximum of two months from the date of obtaining the negative certificate of registered name.

'Granting the public deed'. In this step, once the bylaws have been drafted, the incorporation of the limited company is formalized through the execution of the public deed before a notary. This document includes the negative certification of the name, a copy of the ID of each founding partner, the bank certificate proving the deposit of the share capital, and the bylaws. This procedure must be completed within two months of the negative certification being issued.

Subsequently, the "census declaration" must be submitted to the State Tax Administration Agency (AEAT) to obtain the provisional CIF (Tax Identification Number) and register the company for the IAE (Economic and Business Tax) and the corresponding VAT regime. To do so, photocopies of the articles of incorporation and the partners' IDs must be provided. This procedure must be completed within a period of 30 calendar days from the date of incorporation using Form 036.

Settlement of the Property Transfer Tax (ITP). This procedure involves settling the Tax on Property Transfers and Documented Legal Acts, which is levied upon the incorporation of the company. This procedure is carried out at the branch of the Ministry of Economy of the corresponding Autonomous Community. Form 600 must be submitted along with the deed of incorporation (first copy and certified copy) and the provisional CIF (Tax Identification Number). The process must be completed within 30 business days of the execution of the deed.

The registration of the articles of incorporation in the commercial registry gives the limited company full formal effectiveness. This procedure is carried out at the Commercial Registry of the registered office, where the first copy of the articles of incorporation, the previously processed negative certification of the name, proof of payment of the Property Transfer Tax (ITP AJD), and a photocopy of the provisional CIF must be submitted. The registration period varies between 1 and 2 months, depending on the registration burden and the

type of company. Although some methods, such as "Holded" (Fondevila, 2025) and "EmprenemJunts" (EmprenemJunts) ...*B.03.02. Registration in the Commercial Registry - Memofichas* | *EmprenemJunts*, 2025) testify that this period usually takes between 15 days and two months, although it can be faster, as little as 6 hours, if done through online registration at an Entrepreneur Service Point.

Finally, for the complete tax identification of the new Limited Company, it is essential to obtain the definitive CIF (Tax Identification Number). This procedure is carried out at the provincial office of the AEAT (Spanish Tax Agency) corresponding to the company's tax domicile. The provisional CIF must be submitted along with the original and the first copy of the articles of incorporation already registered in the Commercial Registry. Obtaining the definitive CIF must be done within a maximum of six months from the date of issuance of the provisional CIF.

The governing and management bodies.

First, the choice of governing and management bodies should be based on the level of involvement of each partner, the decision-making structure, and the company's growth prospects. These will be key when choosing between the two most optimal options for siblings:

A sole administrator, in which only one person is chosen to handle the responsibility of managing and representing the company. Even if they are siblings, this can lead to a conflict of interest in the future due to a lack of common understanding of how to act. If this is the case, there may be a governing body. attorney/which consists of appointing a person or group to carry out legal acts in their names.

The other viable option for this case is a joint or several administration of the company: In the joint administration, both parties can exercise management and representation, in which each can act individually, which again will depend on the personality and the responsibilities they are going to assume. This is because there may be disputes both due to conflicts of interest, as with the first option, but also because one of them may end up having to work harder due to ineffectiveness or similar issues that one of them may present. While in the joint administration, although both parties can exercise management and representation, they must act jointly to carry them out. This can generate greater peace of mind for both, having as a counterpart the one whodebanto reach an agreement sooner. This is why, in bureaucratic terms, it is the least

time-efficient. A very good way to resolve this is through an advisory committee, which at first might entail a very high cost due to the hiring/salary of the necessary personnel, but its future implementation, with improved financial results, will provide peace of mind and speed up agreements. This is because an advisory committee is an advisory body whose purpose is to offer recommendations or opinions to the governing bodies for decision-making.

Conclusion.

In summary, after analyzing the particularities of the shampoo trade project proposed by Ms. Lara Simó Roca and Mr. Roger Simó Roca, it is recommended that the incorporation of a Limited Liability Company (LLC) is recommended as the most appropriate legal form for conducting business. This entity, regulated primarily by the Capital Companies Law, offers a favorable balance by limiting the liability of the two partners to the capital contributed, thus protecting their personal assets, although it entails certain formalities and costs for incorporation and management. This report details the specific characteristics of the LLC, breaking down its advantages and disadvantages in the context of its activity, as well as the precise roadmap for its incorporation, including the procedural steps and documentation required at each stage, from the application for a company name (the name of the company) to registration in the Commercial Registry. Furthermore, consideration has been given to how the distribution of share capital could be addressed, reflecting each partner's participation based on their contributions of €15,000 and €5,000, respectively, thereby determining their proportion of the company's shares and the rights and obligations inherent to their status as partners.

Citations.

Niubó Clavé, S. (s.f.). *Creation and legal regime of companies: Corporations*[PDF File].
Barcelona University School of Formatic.

Bsjabogados, & Bsjabogados. (2020, September 25). What does the Capital Companies Act say?

- BSJ Abogados. *BSJ Abogados - Law firm in Alicante*.

<https://bufetesemperejaen.com/que-dice-la-ley-de-sociedades-de-capital/#:~:text=Disponen%20de%20un%20capital%20social,socio%20ante%20las%20deudas%20sociales>.

ConceptosJurídicos.com. (2024, September 4). *Capital Companies Law in Spain [Updated 2025]*.

Legal Concepts. <https://www.conceptosjuridicos.com/ley-sociedades-capital/>

Fondevila, J. (2025, February 13). *How to create a limited company step by step in 2025*. Holded.

<https://www.holded.com/es/blog/como-constituir-una-s-l#:~:text=En%20cuanto%20a%20la%20inscripci%C3%B3n,en%20apenas%206%20horas%20h%C3%A1biles>.

B.03.02. *Registration in the Commercial Registry - Memofichas | EmprenemJunts*. (2025, March 10). www.emprenemjunts.es.

<https://www.emprenemjunts.es/?op=63&n=39#:~:text=El%20registrador%20mercantil%20inscribir%C3%A1%20la,de%20obtenci%C3%B3n%20del%20CIF%20definitivo>.

VLEX | *Free Trial - Spain*. (n.d.). vLex.

https://vlex.es/freetrial/signup/ES?webapp_path=%2Fvid%2F44372674

Types of Companies/Legal Forms. (n.d.). Spin-Offs University of

Granada. <https://spinoff.ugr.es/spinoffs/infobenefit/tipos-de-empresas-formas-juridicas/#3>